

Fluid circulation in the upper Martian crust, Arcadia Planitia (Mars)

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We previously reported on evidence for fluid circulation in the upper crust of Mars, which could create environments favorable for life and its development. We investigated the nature of the thumbprint terrains covering part of Arcadia planitia in the Martian northern hemisphere and we were able to ascribe these morphologies to sedimentary volcanism involving a feeding network of fractures reaching the base of the clathrate-rich cryosphere, where lies the contact with the theoretical underlying hydrosphere. Based on this evidence we are now pursuing a further study to identify the possible trigger to the sediment/water emissions. Accordingly, we enhanced the dataset by enlarging the study area starting from the sample region used in the previous work and then analyzed the spatial distributions of vents and fractures among the new thumbprint terrains population to infer subsurface extension of these fracture networks. We detected a maximum extension of the fracture networks consistent with the ones previously published and identified a formerly unknown shallow rheological discontinuity just a few kilometers underneath the surface. Thanks to this new data load we are producing a more precise picture of the Martian subsurface that will allow us to produce a model displaying how the Martian crust would locally behave under the diverse drives, which would be affected by rheological differences and ice content.

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